

RESPONSE OF THE CELLS OF BACTERIA OF THE GENUS *PSEUDOMONAS* ISOLATED FROM DIFFERENT ANTARCTIC SUBSTRATES TO THE INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF $K_2Cr_2O_7$

O.D. Maslovska, S.Ya. Komplikevych, O.M. Moroz, N.M. Pazur, S.O. Pelekh, S.O. Hnatush
Ivan Franko National University of Lviv, Lviv, Ukraine; olha.maslovska@lnu.edu.ua

Bacteria of the genus *Pseudomonas* are among the most commonly cultivated representatives of the Antarctic microbiota, which can adapt to adverse environmental conditions. One of the mechanisms of metal compounds' effect on cells is the formation of reactive oxygen species and cellular damage caused by free radicals. The purpose of the work was to study the impact of potassium dichromate on the content of lipid peroxidation products and the activity of enzymes of the antioxidant defense system of bacteria of the genus *Pseudomonas* isolated from various Antarctic substrates. The bacteria *Pseudomonas yamanorum* IMB B-7916, *Pseudomonas arsenicoxidans* 89_1T_89, and *Pseudomonas* sp. 3B-in-57, isolated and identified at the Department of Microbiology of Ivan Franko National University of Lviv in different years from samples collected during the 26–27 Ukrainian Antarctic Expeditions were used in the study. The bacteria were grown for 21–32 h (depending on the strain) at 29 ± 1 °C in a tryptic soy broth (TSB) medium containing $K_2Cr_2O_7$ at concentrations of 0.125–0.575 mM (for *P. yamanorum* IMB B-7916), 0.06–0.30 mM (for *P. arsenicoxidans* 89_1T_89) and 0.6–1.4 mM (for *Pseudomonas* sp. 3B-in-57). The study of lipid peroxidation (LPO) and enzymatic activities was carried out in the middle and at the end of the exponential and the beginning of the stationary growth phase of the batch culture.

The $K_2Cr_2O_7$ in the culture medium of the studied bacteria of the genus *Pseudomonas* inhibits the biomass accumulation. During the cultivation of bacteria in TSB, enzymatic and non-enzymatic Cr(VI) reduction reactions occur, likely to form free radical compounds that damage the macromolecules of bacterial cells. The addition of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ to TSB caused an increase in the content of diene conjugates in *P. yamanorum* IMB B-7916, *P. arsenicoxidans* 89_1T_89, and *Pseudomonas* sp. 3B-in-57 cells. In all the studied bacteria, the content of these LPO products increased with increasing concentration of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ in the medium and varied depending on the duration of bacterial cultivation. Besides diene conjugates, the content of lipid hydroperoxides also increased in the cells of the studied strains under the influence of $K_2Cr_2O_7$. Under these conditions, changes in the activity of the enzymes of the antioxidant defense system (superoxide dismutase and catalase) were revealed. In the control, the enzymatic activities of *P. yamanorum* IMB B-7916 were the highest at the 3rd hour of bacterial growth and significantly decreased with increasing duration of cultivation. The addition of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ to TSB caused an increase in the enzymatic activities of *P. yamanorum* IMB B-7916 with an increase in salt concentration. These enzymatic activities decreased with further cultivation, but under the influence of all studied concentrations of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ were higher than in the control. The enzymatic activities of *P. arsenicoxidans* 89_1T_89 changed similarly: the highest values were detected at the 4th h of cultivation, and with an increase in the duration of cultivation to 24 h, their values slightly decreased. When $K_2Cr_2O_7$ was added to the growth medium, enzymatic activities increased with an increase in salt concentration. The superoxide dismutase activity of *Pseudomonas* sp. 3B-in-57 grown without $K_2Cr_2O_7$ was the highest at the 6th hour of cultivation. Under the influence of $K_2Cr_2O_7$, this activity increased significantly with increasing concentration of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ in the medium. After cultivation up to 32 h, superoxide dismutase activity decreased but was 5–21 times higher than in the control. During the growth of *Pseudomonas* sp. 3B-in-57 in the medium with different concentrations of $K_2Cr_2O_7$, no increase in catalase activity was detected compared to the control.

The work was performed under the State Special-Purpose Research Program in Antarctica for 2011–2025.